

Conformation of Mammalian Lens Proteins : Photoinduced Changes in Relation to Cataract Formation[†]

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Although the secondary structures of all lens crystallins are more or less similar, their tertiary structures are remarkably different as manifested in their near-uv circular dichroic and intrinsic or extrinsic fluorescence spectra. Methylene blue-sensitised photooxidation causes a change in the tertiary structure of lens crystallins but in each case subtle differences exist in the nature of the changes. Photoinduced changes in the conformation of lens protein are discussed in terms of destabilisation of the protein structure during cataractogenesis.

FUNCTIONALLY, the lens of the eye must be transparent and highly refractive. The mammalian lens is composed largely of soluble proteins, commonly known as crystallins; three classes α , β , and γ , are distinguished on the basis of chemical characteristics, such as molecular weight (MW) and electrophoretic mobility¹. β -Crystallins can be further separated by gel chromatography into two components² of differing molecular weight, β_H (high) and β_L (low), and γ by ion-exchange chromatography into several fractions³, the major ones being γ -II, γ -III and γ -IV.

The lens contains about 35% (by weight) structural proteins. This high crystallin concentration imparts to the lens its uniformly high refractive index, yet leaves it completely transparent in the normal tissue⁴. Lens transparency may depend on conformation, inter-molecular interactions, and long-range ordering of the densely packed crystallins^{5,6}.

Simply defined, a cataract is a lens opacity that results in loss of transparency and that occurs mainly in the central (nucleus) rather than the peripheral (cortex) region of the tissue. Cataract formation is a slow but irreversible process. Among the physicochemical changes that human lens crystallins undergo during aging and cataractogenesis are increased protein-protein aggregation and formation of insoluble proteins, increased pigmentation in the nucleus, and formation of blue fluorescent products⁷⁻¹¹. The aggregation is stabilised either by disulphide bonds formed by oxidation of sulphhydryl groups of cysteine residues or by unknown covalent non-disulphide crosslinks or possibly by non-covalent associations^{9,10,12}.

Considerable progress has been made in elucidation of the chemical (primary) structure of crystallins^{2,13-15} and the chemical changes in aging and cataractogenesis. However, little is known of the

conformation, the interactions between different segments of the amino acid chains, and the spatial orientation of groups susceptible to chemical change, and the changes of these features during aging and cataractogenesis.

The conformation of a protein is usually described by its secondary and tertiary structures. Because of the interactions between various amino acid side chains and the relative degree of interaction with water, proteins are rarely fully extended, linear chains; instead they fold to form complex, three-dimensional structures. Frequently, monomeric units at some position along the chain engage in specific interactions (mainly hydrogen bonds) with other units close by or at some distance along the linear sequence and form an identifiable substructure called the secondary structure; α -helices and β -sheets in proteins are common examples. Secondary structure carries little, if any, information about spatial orientations. Tertiary structure carries no identifiable features, but it provides information about orientation and describes all of the interactions of all atoms of the protein in three-dimensional space. The interactions, obviously, are related to the spatial distribution of atoms or groups of atoms and their micro-environments.

The three-dimensional structure of γ -II crystallin has been determined in great detail from X-ray analysis by Blundel and coworkers¹⁶⁻¹⁷. The protein's stability was ascribed to its high degree of internal symmetry. γ -III and γ -IV also have internal structural symmetry, with predominantly β -sheet structure folded into domains¹⁸. Spectroscopic analysis of the secondary and tertiary structure of α -, β -, and γ -crystallins¹⁹⁻²² have provided data on the conformation of lens protein in solution. We have noted changes in tertiary structure in the presence of sugar molecules²³ and in aging²⁴.

[†] Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

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The possible role of light in the etiology of human cataract is of intense research interest²⁵⁻³¹, because the eye is a major photoreceptor organ of the body and because photooxidation of tryptophan (Trp) (amino acid residue abundant in lens protein) yields pigmented and fluorescent oxidation products, some of which are present in mature or cataractous lens. Photochemical damage to the lens protein involves formation of covalent disulphide and non-disulphide crosslinks^{26,28,30}.

We have undertaken³²⁻³⁵ a systematic investigation of the light-induced conformational changes of lens crystallins using various spectroscopic techniques—absorption, fluorescence, and circular dichroism (CD). The present paper briefly outlines the structural aspects of lens crystallins, reports results of our studies of photoinduced conformational changes of crystallins, particularly β - and γ -, and discusses the mechanism of such processes.

Experimental

The cortex (70-80% of lens volume) was removed from lenses (0.9-1.0 g) from 1- to 2-week-old calves, and the water-soluble proteins were extracted and fractionated by gel and ion-exchange chromatography^{32,34}. The ultra-pure chemicals used were bought commercially. Protein solutions were dialysed at 4° against respective buffers, just prior to spectroscopic analysis. Protein concentration was determined with a standard absorption value at 280 nm³² or by the Lowry method³⁶. β - and γ -Crystallins used for photochemical studies were unfractionated samples; β - contained both β_H and β_L , and γ - was a mixture of its subfractions, γ -I to γ -IV.

Fluorescence was measured on a Perkin-Elmer MPF-44A spectrofluorometer and CD spectra on a AVIV 60 DS CD spectropolarimeter modified as described previously^{19,22}. Absorption was recorded on a Beckman DU-8 spectrophotometer. The protein sample in the presence of methylene blue (MB) was irradiated in a set-up described previously³².

Results

The near-uv spectra of all crystallins and the far-uv spectra of β - (which represents other crystallins also) are shown in Figs. 1-4. The far-uv CD of all crystallins are similar, but not identical^{19,21,22}; all show a minimum around 216 nm (Fig. 3, inset), which is characteristic of beta-sheet conformation. Further information on the secondary structure was obtained from curve-fitting methods²⁷⁻²⁹ of CD spectra and X-ray¹⁶ analysis (Table 1). The near-uv CD of the crystallins are *not* similar: intensity, peak, and shoulder positions vary. γ -Crystallins, in addition, show intense rotational strength around 235 nm; among γ -crystallins distinct differences exist in the 225-250 and 280-320

nm regions (Fig. 1). Vibrational progressions of phenylalanine (Phe) are prominent in α -; thus, the CD between 250-280 nm is more structured than that of β - and γ -. Based on absorption, pH difference absorption, and pH difference CD spectra^{19,22}, we have assigned the near-uv CD bands of all crystallins (Table 2).

The quantum yield and emission maxima for native and denatured crystallins are given in Table 3. In the native form, emission maxima (excited at 280-295 nm) of all crystallins were shifted to a wavelength shorter than that of free Trp, which emits at 350 nm. γ -II showed a maximum blue

Fig. 1. Near-uv CD spectra of γ -crystallin in 20 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.0): (—) γ -II, (---) γ -III and (-·-·) γ -IV.

Fig. 2. Near-uv CD spectra of α -crystallin: (—) control and (---) irradiated in daylight at 37° for 1.5 h. Reaction mixture for photolysis contains 2.4 mg ml⁻¹ of protein and 10⁻⁵ M MB in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.4).

Fig. 3. Near-uv and far-uv (inset) CD spectra of β -crystallin: (—) control; irradiated at 37° in daylight for (---) 1.5 and (-.-) 6 h. Reaction mixture for photolysis contains 1 mg ml^{-1} of protein and 10^{-4} M MB in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.4).

Fig. 4. Near-uv CD spectra of γ -crystallin: (—) control, (---) control labeled with iodoacetamide and (-.-) iodoacetamide-labeled control irradiated for 0.5 h. Experimental conditions same as in Fig. 3.

shift to 324 nm , and α -crystallin showed the least shift, to 336 nm . In the presence of a protein denaturant, 6 M guanidine hydrochloride or 8 M

Curve-fitting method or other	Protein (crystallin)	Percentage			
		α -helix	β -sheet	Random coil	β -turn
Brahms and Brahms ^a	α	0	45	37	18
	β_H	0	51	42	7
	β_L	8	48	40	4
	γ -II	0	61	28	11
	γ -III	0	58	29	13
Hennessey and Johnson ^b	γ -IV	0	52	31	17
	α	3	53	28	16
	β_H	0	60	22	18
	β_L	7	70	19	4
	γ -II	5	56	24	15
X-ray crystallography ^c	γ -III	5	46	31	18
	γ -IV	5	45	30	20
	γ -II	25 ^e	49	←26→ (undefined)	

[†] Compiled from Refs. 16, 21, and 22 and from unpublished data.

^a These are not true alpha-helix, as all are distorted and short. Calculation is strictly on the basis of ϕ/ψ bond angles.

^b Refs. 37 and 38. ^c Ref. 39. ^e Ref. 16.

urea, the emission maxima shift to longer wavelengths. A shoulder around 305 nm (not shown) due to tyrosine (Tyr) emission can be seen in some crystallins when they are denatured^{1,2}.

In the MB-sensitized reactions, the near-uv CD spectra of all crystallins change (Figs. 2-4). In the far-uv CD, the CD minimum at 216 nm for both α -^{3,4} and β - remain unaltered even after 6 h of irradiation; however, the decrease in intensity (Fig. 3, inset) indicates a slight decrease in the beta-sheet content. Although the photodynamic actions on α -crystallin have been studied in detail by using 300 nm radiation^{3,5} and in the presence of MB^{3,5,6} or riboflavin^{3,5} (RF), for comparison we have shown a near-uv spectrum of α -crystallin after 1.5 h irradiation. Between α - and β -, there are distinct differences in the near-uv spectra of 1.5 h irradiated samples; for example, for α - the $0.0 \text{ }^1\text{L}_a$ Trp band at 295 nm disappears, but for β - the band exists even after 6 h of irradiation. It appears that for α -, both $^1\text{L}_a$ and $^1\text{L}_b$ Trp band are equally affected, whereas for β - the $^1\text{L}_a$ Trp band changes significantly. After 6 h of irradiation, predominantly the Phe vibrational structure is visible for α -^{3,4}, whereas the spectrum of β - tends to become negative. In addition, $0.0 \text{ }^1\text{L}_b$ Tyr, $0+850 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ Tyr, $^1\text{L}_b$ Trp, and vibronic Phe are still identifiable for β -.

Both α - and β -crystallin solutions remained clear over a long period of irradiation. However, γ -solution became turbid during irradiation, the onset of turbidity depending upon the protein concentration. Assuming that the turbidity arises from the disulphide crosslinks, SH groups of β -crystallin were labeled with iodoacetamide^{4,6}. Upon irradiation of such a sample (0.06 mg ml^{-1}), no turbidity was observed even on 6 h irradiation, whereas the unlabelled protein became turbid in 2 h. However,

TABLE 2—ASSIGNMENTS OF NEAR-UV CD BANDS

α	β_H	β_L	γ -II	γ -III	γ -IV
-292 (0-0 1L_b Trp)*	-297 (0-0 1L_b Trp)	-295 (0-0 1L_b Trp)	-299 (0-0 1L_b Trp)	-298 (0-0 1L_b Trp)	-300 (0-0 1L_b Trp)
-286 (0+ $\sim$ 950 cm^{-1} 1L_b Trp)	+286 (superimposed 0+ $\sim$ 950 cm^{-1} 1L_b Trp and 1L_b Tyr)	+283 (superimposed 0+ $\sim$ 950 cm^{-1} 1L_b Trp and 1L_b Tyr)	-288 (superimposed 0+ $\sim$ 950 cm^{-1} + 0-0 1L_b Tyr negative)	-289 (superimposed 0+950 cm^{-1} + 0-0 1L_b Tyr negative)	+288 (0-0 1L_b Tyr positive)
+281 (0-0 1L_b Tyr)	—	—	—	—	—
+272 (0+ $\sim$ 800 cm^{-1} 1L_b Tyr)	+276 (0+ $\sim$ 800 cm^{-1} 1L_b Tyr)	+275 (0+ $\sim$ 800 cm^{-1} 1L_b Tyr)	+270 (0+800 cm^{-1} 1L_b Tyr)	+270 (0+800 cm^{-1} 1L_b Tyr)	+275 (0+ $\sim$ 800 cm^{-1} 1L_b Tyr)
+266 (superimposed 1L_a Trp+Phe)**	+267 (superimposed 1L_a Trp+Phe)	+265 (superimposed 1L_a Trp+Phe)	+250 to 266 region (superimposed 1L_a Trp+Phe)	+250 to 266 region (superimposed 1L_a Trp+Phe)	+250 to 266 region (superimposed 1L_a Trp+Phe)
+258 (superimposed Phe+ 1L_a Trp)	+261 (superimposed 1L_a Trp+Phe)	+254 (superimposed 1L_a Trp+Phe)	-245 and +235 (exciton bands of 1L_a Tyr)	+235 (exciton bands of 1L_a Tyr)	+235 and -245 (exciton bands of 1L_a Tyr)
+255 (superimposed Phe+ 1L_a Trp)	+253 (superimposed 1L_a Trp+Phe)	—	—	—	—

Based on absorption, and difference (pH 8-11.5) CD and absorption spectra; for details Refs. 19 and 22 may be seen.

* -294 indicates negative OD band (or shoulder) at 294 nm; band assignments are given in the parenthesis.

** 1L_a Trp is actually a broad structureless band located at the 260 to 280 nm region.

TABLE 3—FLUORESCENCE PARAMETERS OF LENS CRYSTALLINS†

Crystallin	Native		Denatured in guanidine hydrochloride	
	λ_{max}	ϕ Trp*	λ_{max} **	ϕ Trp
α	336	0.186	350 (350)	0.118
β_H	334	0.102	350 (350)	0.128
β_L	334	0.106	350 (350)	0.121
γ -II	324	0.065	344 (336)	(mixtures of the
γ -III	329	0.105	350 (336)	three, 0.142)
γ -IV	334	0.121	350 (336)	

† Compiled from Refs. 19 and 22.

* Quantum yields, ϕ , were obtained by excitation at 295 nm.

** Values in parentheses, in urea.

a concentrated solution (1 mg ml⁻¹) of the labeled protein became turbid upon irradiation for 1 h or less, indicating that non-disulphide aggregation is also involved. For CD measurements, we used 1 mg ml⁻¹ of this protein solution and irradiated for 0.5 h. Even though no appreciable turbidity was observed, the solution was filtered through a 0.22 μ m Millipore filter prior to measurement.

Labeling with iodoacetamide does not alter the near-uv CD of γ -crystallin significantly, but labeled γ -, upon MB-sensitised irradiation for 0.5 h, shows a change (Fig. 5) that is similar to that of α -crystallin²⁴ irradiated for the same time. An increase in the 250 nm band with distinct vibrational peaks of Phe is seen. This has been attributed to a sign reversal of Phe transitions from negative to positive by the generated 1O_2 and the sensitizer²⁴; in the normal near-uv CD of all crystallins we assigned the dichroic bands of Phe as negative¹⁹. In the case of β -, however, Phe bands still remain negative after 6 h of irradiation.

Fig. 5 shows a red shift (4-5 nm) of Trp emission of β -crystallin after sensitised irradiation.

Fig. 5. Trp fluorescence (λ_{ex} 295 nm) of a reaction mixture same as in Fig. 3: (—) control; (---) irradiated for 1.5 h and (---) irradiated for 6 h. Irradiation conditions same as in Fig. 3. Intensity scale for 6 h is 10 times that of the control. (---) Non-Trp (N-FK type) fluorescence (λ_{ex} 320 nm) after 6 h of irradiation with sensitivity scale 10 times that of control for Trp fluorescence. (Inset) Time course in percent loss of Trp fluorescence: (—) β -crystallin (1 mg ml⁻¹) and (---) γ -crystallin (0.06 mg ml⁻¹). Experimental conditions same as in Fig. 3.

The inset shows the kinetics of Trp photooxidation for β - and γ -. However, no significant shift (as was observed²⁴ for α -crystallin) in the steady-state emission in MIANS (6-[4'-maleimidylanilino]naphthalene-2-sulphonic acid)-labeled β -crystallin was observed, presumably because thiol groups of β - are already in a polar environment²⁰.

Discussion

Our studies of lens proteins have two objectives, (i) to elucidate the structural features of the individual crystallins that endow them with stability and the interactions between them that give rise to a highly ordered, transparent structure, and (ii) to understand the cause and mechanism by which these proteins aggregate and the lens loses transparency during cataractogenesis.

Although three-dimensional structural analyses have suggested that all the γ -crystallins, and possibly β -, have the same highly symmetrical, two-domain, antiparallel, beta-sheet backbone structure as described for γ -II¹⁵⁻¹⁷, considerable differences have been noted in the spectral properties of α -, β - and γ -crystallins, and also of γ -II, γ -III and γ -IV¹⁹⁻²².

The assessments from curve-fitting methods of far-uv CD spectra support the notion that all crystallins have very similar secondary structures, namely, 50% or more beta-sheet (presumably all antiparallel) and little or no alpha-helix. Yet subtle differences exist in the shape of the far-uv CD spectra^{21,22}.

The tertiary structure of a protein in solution can be conveniently assessed from its near-uv CD and fluorescence spectra, provided the protein contains aromatic acid residues, particularly Trp and Tyr. Lens proteins are generally rich in such residues, and thus their tertiary structures may be important with respect to stability²³. The theoretical aspects of the near-uv CD and its relevance to a protein's tertiary structure have been extensively reviewed²⁴. The aromatic rings of Phe, Tyr, and Trp gain their near-uv CD through interactions with each other or even with the peptide backbone. The mechanisms of interaction by which an unsymmetric environment (of aromatic residues) may induce CD bands are either one electron, or μ -m, and/or μ - μ coupling. The position, intensity, and sign of the near-uv CD bands are not only dependent on these interaction parameters but are also strongly influenced by the microenvironment of the aromatic side chains, e.g. hydrogen bonding, polar or charged groups, and polarisability. Most importantly, some aromatic side chains may be on the surface and exposed mainly to water but still have contact with other moieties. Buried chains may exist in a variety of environments ranging from non-polar (hydrophobic) to polar (hydrophilic). Both near-uv CD and fluorescence spectroscopy can provide information on the microenvironments of the aromatic residues, and the two techniques have been combined to detail the tertiary structure of lens crystallins in solution¹⁹⁻²⁴.

In contrast to secondary structure, the tertiary structures of lens crystallins differ considerably, as manifested in their near-uv CDs (Figs. 1-4) and fluorescence properties (Table 3). This is mostly

due to the fact that the microenvironments of Trp, Tyr, and Cys residues are not the same in each crystallin^{20,22}. For example, Trp residues in γ -crystallins are buried in the hydrophobic interior of the protein, and α - and β -crystallins they are presumably in more polar environments; from emission maxima and quantum yield values it has been suggested that the hydrophobicity of Trp environments decreases in the order, γ -II $>$ γ -III $>$ γ -IV $>$ β $>$ α . The order is more or less reversed²⁰ in the case of Cys residues as is evident from the fluorescent parameters of MIANS-labeled SH groups of Cys. Differences in the microenvironments of these residues indicate that their spatial arrangements, reactivities, or accessibilities to reactants are not similar.

The remarkable differences in the tertiary structures of lens crystallins may well account for the low-temperature aggregation²⁵ of γ -crystallin, loss of solubility of α -crystallin with aging^{1,9}, and ease of disulphide formation in β -crystallin². Although lens crystallins have very symmetrical structures that may confer stability in the normal healthy lens, any change, metabolic or environmental (light), could disrupt the arrangements of these reactive groups (Trp, Tyr, or Cys) and alter their interaction properties, leading to loss of transparency¹⁰.

We have previously shown²² that irradiation of α -crystallin by 300 nm light causes considerable photooxidation of Trp residues with the formation of N-formylkynurenine (N-FK)-type products. Since N-FK is an effective sensitizer²⁶, the observed conformational change is essentially a sensitizer-induced process. α -Crystallin also undergoes a major conformational change in a dye-sensitized (MB or RF) reaction^{24,25}. In general, a photosensitizer in the presence of an oxidisable substrate (e.g. amino acid or protein) follows two major pathways²⁷ upon excitation, as illustrated below.

Using inhibitors specific for the active species of oxygen, it has been shown²⁴ that, in the MB-sensitized reaction, singlet oxygen ${}^1\text{O}_2$ (type II) and

sensitiser itself play a major role in the conformational change of α -crystallin. In contrast, the RF²⁵ or N-FK^{23,24}-sensitised reaction, a type II process, is less significant, and in the case of N-FK, conformational change is not as drastic as with MB or RF.

The secondary structure of β - following photo-sensitisation remains virtually unaltered as manifested in the far-uv CD whereas the near-uv CD (tertiary structure) and fluorescence change drastically. A red shift in the Trp emission indicates that some residues that were buried in the non-polar regions of the protein are now exposed. This is supported by the fact that the rate of Trp photo-oxidation is significantly faster in the MB-sensitised reaction (Fig. 5, inset) than upon irradiation by 300 nm light²².

γ -Crystallin behaves very differently from β - and α - in that the protein solution becomes turbid upon irradiation for 1 h in the presence of MB. Since we observe a significant change in the near-uv CD of γ -crystallin irradiated for 0.5 h (Fig. 4), the turbidity is very likely preceded by conformational change.

In this study, we have demonstrated that MB-sensitised photooxidation reaction causes a change in tertiary structure of lens crystallins but in each case subtle differences exist in the nature of the changes. In a sensitised reaction, only Cys, methionine, histidine, Trp, and Tyr residues of a protein are vulnerable to photooxidation^{4,5}. The ease and extent of oxidation of these residues are dependent on their sequence, spatial orientation and micro-environments, and these in turn reflect the tertiary structure of the protein. Thus, it is the difference in tertiary structure observed among the crystallins^{19,20} that is responsible for the variations in the nature of the photoinduced conformational changes.

There is enough evidence to indicate that disruption in the protein structure can be caused by a photosensitised reaction that could eventually lead to cataract formation. However, normal lens contains inhibitors—superoxide dismutase, ascorbate, catalase, and glutathione—that scavenge the superoxide anion (O_2^-), $\cdot OH$, H_2O_2 , and quench 1O_2 and triplet sensitiser. Lack of these protective mechanisms will favour photoinduced changes in the protein structure, particularly when the sensitisers riboflavin (vitamin B) and N-FK have been identified in the lens²⁶.

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